

Supplementary Figures

Revision of recluse spiders (Sicariidae: *Loxosceles*) preserved in Dominican amber and a total-evidence phylogeny of Scytodoidea reveal the first fossil Drymusidae

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Arthropod Systematics and Phylogeny

Figure S1. Maximum likelihood tree from target-gene molecular markers (12S, 16S, COI, H3, 18S, 28S), estimated with IQ-TREE, with 1000 ultrafast bootstrap rounds.

Figure S2. Maximum likelihood tree from the UCE genomic dataset, estimated with IQ-TREE, with 1000 ultrafast bootstrap rounds.

Figure S3. Trees from the molecular partition (UCE + target-genes). Left, maximum likelihood tree estimated with IQ-TREE, with 1000 ultrafast bootstrap rounds. Right, maximum parsimony tree estimated with TNT, with 1000 bootstrap rounds.

Figure S4. Trees from the morphological partition. Left, maximum likelihood tree estimated with IQ-TREE, with 1000 ultrafast bootstrap rounds. Right, maximum parsimony consensus tree estimated with TNT, with 1000 bootstrap rounds.

Figure S5. Total evidence dataset. Left, maximum likelihood tree estimated with IQ-TREE, with 1000 ultrafast bootstrap rounds. Right, maximum parsimony tree estimated with TNT, with 1000 bootstrap rounds. Note: the branches resolved in the ML tree (but not in the MP tree) are not supported by any synapomorphy, molecular or morphological, and have been collapsed for Fig. 6.